

FACTORS AFFECTING THE BEHAVIOR OF CHOOSING HEALTH CARE SERVICES AT PRIVATE HOSPITALS IN HANOI CITY

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Abstract

The research report focuses on researching factors affecting the behavior of citizens choosing medical examination and treatment at private hospitals in Hanoi city. With rapid and uneven population growth, Hanoi faces major challenges in its public health system, including financial constraints, lack of medical human resources, and service delivery capacity. The study focuses on factors affecting Hanoi people's decision to choose a private hospital, including: (i) Attitude towards private hospitals; (ii) Subjective norms; (iii) Perceived behavioral control; (iv) Perceived benefits; (v) Healthcare costs; (vi) Motivation for seeking healthcare at private hospitals. The results show that subjective norms, cost, motivation and perceived benefits have a significant influence on the intention to seek medical treatment at a private hospital. Meanwhile, perceived behavioral control and attitude towards private hospitals do not have enough statistical significance to conclude about the influence of these variables on the intention to seek medical treatment at private hospitals. Intention to seek medical treatment at a private hospital has a strong influence on choice behavior, with an influence level of 0.918. The research results will provide important information about people's trends and priorities in choosing private hospitals, and also propose solutions to improve service quality and development strategies of private hospitals in Hanoi.

Keywords: Health Care, Medical Treatment, Private Hospitals, the Factors Affecting Intention.

1. INTRODUCTION

Hanoi's population growth rate is quite high and uneven among units, mainly due to mechanical population growth, with an average increase of about 69.1 thousand people/year. Hanoi's population density in 2022 is 2,511 people/km², ranking 2nd in the country, meanwhile there is a big difference between rural areas and urban areas (Phuong Nga, 2023). To meet the health care needs of the population, the public health system has faced challenges including the limited ability to increase financial space for health spending, lack of capital resources, health human resources, and capacity and quality of services provided (Nguyen and Wilson, 2017). Therefore, in the health care system of a crowded city like Hanoi, the existence of two health care systems, private and public, contributes to ensuring the medical examination and treatment needs of the people. Currently in Hanoi city, the public sector has 41 hospitals, including 29 city hospitals and 13 district hospitals (Huy Son, 2023). With the strong development of the economy and population growth at the same time as the development of medicine and technology, people have increasingly higher demands for quality and effective medical services.

Statistics from the Ministry of Health also show that, over the past 10 years, Vietnam's total health expenditure per capita has increased by an average of 11%/year. The average number of visits to the hospital for medical examination and treatment per Vietnamese person has increased from 1.89 visits/year to 2.95 visits/year over the past 10 years. However, it is still much lower than other countries in the region such as Thailand (3.5 visits/year), China (4.9 visits/year) and some significantly higher countries such as Japan (12.2 visits/year). According to the World Health Organization (WHO), the growth rate for global health expenditure is 3.9%, higher than the average growth rate of GDP in the world of 3.0%.

The current state of private hospital selection in Hanoi city reflects some clear trends. One of those trends is the significant growth of private medical facilities in recent times. Private hospitals vary in size, from small clinics to large and modern hospitals, providing a wide range of medical services from examination, diagnosis, treatment to rehabilitation and surgery. This diversity provides people with more choices and increases competition in the healthcare sector. In the context of the overload of the public hospital system, the division of medical examination and treatment with health insurance and the existing problems of local healthcare institutes motivate patients in rural areas to choose medical examination and treatment at public hospitals in Hanoi city which leads to overloading. This is the basic reason leading to patients' tendency to choose health care services at private hospitals.

However, choosing a private hospital also poses many challenges for the citizens. One of the most important challenges is ensuring the quality of medical examination and treatment. This can lead to hospitals ordering unnecessary treatments, prescribing unknown medications, or even putting the patient's safety at risk. Another challenge is accessibility and cost. Although private hospitals can provide quick and effective health care services, the cost of these services is often higher than that of public hospitals. This may increase the financial burden for some citizens, especially low-income citizens. In addition, the choice of private hospitals also depends on the geographical location of the hospital, and some people may have difficulty accessing private medical facilities due to long distances or inconvenient transportation.

The report focuses on researching the tendency of people choosing private hospitals for medical examination and treatment in Hanoi city based on factors affecting the community's decision to choose a private hospital. Based on the research overview and reality in Hanoi, in this study, the authors will build a research model with the intention of including the following variables:

- (i) Attitude towards private hospitals;
- (ii) Subjective norms;
- (iii) Perceived behavioral control;
- (iv) Perceived benefits;
- (v) Healthcare costs;
- (vi) Motivation for seeking healthcare at private hospitals.

The independent variable of the study is “Intention to seek medical treatment at a private hospital” and the dependent variable of the study is “Behavior to seek medical treatment at a private hospital”. The research team will conduct a large-scale survey in Hanoi city using random and snowball methods to collect data and use SMARTPLS software to solve the research problems. The results of the study will provide valuable information about people's trends and priorities in choosing private hospitals, and propose specific solutions to improve service quality and development strategies of private hospitals in Hanoi city.

2. THEORETICAL BASIS

2.1. Concepts

Healthcare Services include activities performed by healthcare professionals such as diagnosis and treatment for patients and their families. Diagnosis involves taking medical history, conducting physical examinations, and, if necessary, ordering laboratory tests and functional investigations to make a diagnosis and recommend an appropriate and recognized treatment method. Treatment involves using recognized professional techniques and approved medications for emergency care, treatment, patient care, and rehabilitation. Private Hospitals are healthcare facilities invested and managed by individuals, organizations, or private enterprises. Unlike public hospitals, private hospitals operate based on private capital and typically provide medical services on a business model, meaning all healthcare services come with corresponding costs. Private hospitals often aim to provide high-quality, prompt, and professional healthcare services to meet the increasing healthcare needs of the population.

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), private hospitals play an important role in a nation's healthcare system, helping to reduce the burden on public hospitals and providing more diverse service options for the public (World Health Organization, 2020). This is particularly important in densely populated areas and where the public healthcare system faces significant resource constraints.

2.2. Literature Review

Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA): The Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) was developed by Fishbein and Ajzen in 1975. It focuses on consumer behavior and determines their behavioral intentions, with behavioral intention being partly influenced by attitudes toward the behavior and partly by subjective norms (the influence of others also affecting their attitudes). This model predicts and explains the tendency to perform a behavior better through attitudes toward the behavior rather than through attitudes toward the product or service.

Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB): The Theory of Planned Behavior is an extension and improvement of the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) by Ajzen and Fishbein (1975). It is commonly used to predict specific behaviors of individuals, such as purchasing products or services. The two main factors influencing the decision are personal attitudes and subjective norms. Personal attitudes are measured by beliefs and evaluations of the outcomes of the behavior. Ajzen (1991) defines subjective norms as the perception of whether important others think the individual should or should not perform a particular behavior.

Table 1: Research Overview on Trends in Choosing Private Hospitals

Influencing Factors	Research Scope	Source
Education level, economic status, residence, household size, household with elderly and/or young children, healthcare costs, accessibility, and availability of healthcare services.	India	Rout, Sahu and Mahapatra, 2019
(1) Demographics, (2) Facilities, (3) Convenience, (4) Service quality	Oman	Al-Balushi và Khan (2017)
(1) Facilities, (2) Doctors and staff, (3) Hospital environment, (4) Service quality, (5) Price, (6) Promotions	Tabriz, Iran	Raadabadi et al (2016)
(1) Basic amenities; (2) Reputation; (3) Service quality; (4) Infrastructure; (5) Convenience; (6) Friendliness and sharing; (7) Range of services.	Northern India	Kamra; Singh. và De (2016)
(1) Service quality; (2) Word of mouth; (3) Specialties; (4) Health insurance; (5) Patient satisfaction; (6) Service costs.	Ghana	Bamfo (2017)
(1) Household economy; (2) Administrative procedures; (3) Waiting time; (4) Costs; (5) Service quality; (6) Health insurance.	Urban areas of Vietnam	Phuong., O. T. M., (2016)
(1) Hospital reputation; (2) Quality of medical services; (3) Convenience; (4) Doctor's advice; (5) Family and friends' advice; (6) Facilities and equipment; (7) Attitude of healthcare staff; (8) Hospital fees.	Obstetric services in Ho Chi Minh City	Hy., D. N. G., (2014)
(1) Service quality; (2) Professional quality; (3) Effectiveness of medical treatment; (4) Treatment costs; (5) Type of insurance; (6) Accessibility; (7) Personal characteristics of customers.	Ho Chi Minh City	Cuong., N. T. K., (2013)
Health insurance status, health condition, area of residence, income level	Vietnam	Huong., N.T.T & Van., N.T.T. (2020)

Source: Compiled by the research team

Although there are differences in factors, research scope, and socio-economic and cultural contexts, some prominent points from the research overview include:

- Higher-income individuals prefer private healthcare services over public ones (Rout, Sahu, and Mahapatra, 2019). Urban households tend to favor private hospitals, whereas rural households tend to prefer public healthcare services. Affordability and payment mechanisms, whether out-of-pocket or insured, play a role in patients' decisions regarding the use of public or private healthcare services.
- Health insurance is a crucial factor in deciding the choice of public healthcare facilities (Ayenew et al., 2017; Chatterjee et al., 2018).
- In Vietnam, health insurance participation, severe illness, and living standard variables strongly influence the choice of public or private healthcare facilities by households. The most significant influence on choosing public healthcare facilities in this study is health insurance participation. Households with at least one insured member are 3.45 times more likely to use public healthcare facilities than those without insured members. The second strongest influence on the decision to use public healthcare services is health status. Additionally, older age groups, household composition, ethnicity, place of residence, and

education level are all important in decisions related to the use of public and private healthcare services. Results from this study indicate that private healthcare facilities are not yet the choice of the majority of Vietnamese people, especially for inpatient care (Huong, N.T.T & Van, N.T.T., 2020). Conversely, Thang's (2017) study shows that perceptions of poor diagnostic and treatment quality in public healthcare facilities, the belief that they will receive better treatment in private healthcare facilities, and the convenience of accessing healthcare services can also be significant reasons why some groups choose private healthcare facilities.

Thus, the research focuses on the trends in choosing public versus private hospitals and the factors affecting patient behavior indicates that applying consumer behavior theories, the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), and the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), as well as considering the unique characteristics of choosing private hospitals for healthcare such as costs, benefits, motivations, and the severity of illness, has not been adequately addressed in previous studies. Furthermore, very few studies have been conducted in Hanoi. This provides a basis for the research group to propose a research model on the behavior of choosing private hospitals for healthcare in Hanoi.

2.3. Proposed Model, Research Hypotheses, and Measurement Scales

Based on clarifying the theories of choosing private hospitals for healthcare and consumer behavior theories, the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), and the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), along with some studies on behavioral trends in using healthcare services, the research group proposes the following model, hypotheses, and measurement scales.

Figure 1: Proposed Research Model

Source: Proposed by the research group

Hypothesis and Measurement Scales:

- **Hypothesis H1:** *Attitude toward healthcare services at private hospitals is positively correlated with the intention to seek healthcare at private hospitals (YD).*

Table 2: Observational Variables for the Factor “Attitude toward Healthcare at Private Hospitals”

No.	Symbol	Observational Variable	Reference Source
I	TD	Attitude toward healthcare at private hospitals	Ajen, I (1991); Armitage, C. J., & Conner, M. (1999); Cuong., N. T. K., (2013)
1	TD1	I feel satisfied when receiving healthcare at private hospitals	
2	TD2	I feel that healthcare at private hospitals brings many benefits	
3	TD3	I trust the treatment and healthcare capabilities of private hospitals	
4	TD4	I feel that seeking healthcare at private hospitals is a current trend	
5	TD5	I feel that seeking healthcare at private hospitals is something everyone should experience	

Source: Compiled and proposed by the research team

- **Hypothesis H2:** *Subjective norms (CCQ) are positively correlated with the intention of choosing treatment at private hospitals (YD).*

Subjective norms are often used to measure personal factors that people evaluate or experience. This includes concepts such as awareness, satisfaction, perspectives, or personal evaluations of an event, product, or service.

Table 3: Measurement Scale for the Variable “Subjective Norms”

STT	Symbol	Measurement Scale	Reference Source
II	CCQ	Subjective Norms	Ajen, I (1991); Armitage, C. J., & Conner, M. (1999); Hy., D. N. G., (2014)
6	CCQ1	Friends and people around me advise me to seek healthcare at private hospitals	
7	CCQ2	Doctors, healthcare workers, and influential people in the healthcare field advise me to seek healthcare at private hospitals	
8	CCQ3	I seek healthcare at private hospitals because I think friends and relatives around me have the intention/are using this service	

Source: Compiled and proposed by the research team

- **Hypothesis H3:** *Perceived behavioral control (NT) is positively correlated with the intention of choosing treatment at private hospitals (YD).*

According to Ajzen (1991), perceived behavioral control is an individual's assessment of the degree of control they believe they have in performing a specific behavior. This includes factors such as ability, resources, and external conditions that individuals believe may influence their ability to perform that behavior. Armitage and Conner (1999) expanded the concept of perceived behavioral control by emphasizing factors such as confidence, perceived ability, and power to perform the behavior.

Table 4: Measurement Scale for the Variable “Perceived Behavioral Control”

STT	Symbol	Measurement Scale	Reference Source
III	NT	Perceived Behavioral Control	Ajen, I (1991); Armitage, C. J., & Conner, M. (1999); Truong, N.X. (2019)
9	NT1	My time available is suitable for seeking healthcare at private hospitals	
10	NT2	I have the financial conditions for seeking healthcare at private hospitals	
11	NT3	My health condition is suitable for seeking healthcare at private hospitals	
12	NT4	I have enough knowledge and information to choose seeking healthcare at private hospitals	

Source: Compiled and proposed by the research team

- **Hypothesis H4:** *Perceived benefits (LI) are positively correlated with the intention of choosing treatment at private hospitals (YD).*

Table 5: Measurement Scale for the Variable “Perceived Benefits”

STT	Symbol	Measurement Scale	Reference Source
IV	LI	Perceived Benefits	Kamra; Singh. và De (2016)
13	LI1	Seeking healthcare at private hospitals provides me with better service	
14	LI2	The healthcare environment at private hospitals makes me feel comfortable	
15	LI3	The location of private hospitals is convenient for my travel	
16	LI4	Seeking healthcare at private hospitals reduces my waiting time	

Source: Compiled and proposed by the research team

- **Hypothesis H5:** *Healthcare costs (CP) are positively correlated with the intention of choosing treatment at private hospitals (YD).*

Price value is understood as the perceived balance by consumers between the benefits provided by a service and the monetary cost to use them (Venkatesh et al., 2012). Price has a positive influence when consumers perceive the benefits they receive to be greater than the costs they incur.

Table 6: Measurement Scale for the Variable “Healthcare Costs”

STT	Symbol	Measurement Scale	Reference Source
V	CP	Healthcare Costs	Hy., D. N. G., (2014) Phuong., O. T. M., (2016)
17	CP1	The cost of seeking healthcare at private hospitals is suitable for my financial capability	
18	CP2	The cost of seeking healthcare at private hospitals is appropriate for the benefits received	
19	CP3	The cost of seeking healthcare at private hospitals is appropriate for the experience received	

Source: Compiled and proposed by the research team

- **Hypothesis H6:** Motivation for seeking healthcare (DC) is positively correlated with the intention of choosing treatment at private hospitals (YD).

Table 7: Measurement Scale for the Variable “Motivation for Seeking Healthcare at Private Hospitals”

STT	Symbol	Measurement Scale	Reference Source
VI	DC	Motivation for Seeking Healthcare at Private Hospitals	Cuong., N. T. K., (2013) Kamra; Singh. và De (2016) Raadabadi et al (2016)
20	DC1	I seek healthcare at private hospitals because of high-quality healthcare services	
21	DC2	I seek healthcare at private hospitals because of shorter waiting times	
22	DC3	I seek healthcare at private hospitals because of the convenience and flexibility in the healthcare process	
23	DC4	I seek healthcare at private hospitals because of the friendliness and gentleness of the doctors	
24	DC5	I seek healthcare at private hospitals because of the transparency of treatment costs	

Source: Compiled and proposed by the research team

- **Hypothesis H7:** The Intention of choosing treatment at Private Hospitals (YD) is positively correlated with the behavior of choosing treatment at Private Hospitals (HV).

Table 8: Measurement Scale for the Variables “Intention and Behavior of Choosing Treatment at Private Hospitals”

STT	Symbol	Measurement Scale	Reference Source
VII	YD	Intention of choosing treatment at Private Hospitals	Ajen, I (1991); Al-Balushi & Khan (2017)
25	YD1	I intend to seek healthcare at private hospitals in the near future	
26	YD2	I will pay more attention to healthcare services at private hospitals	
27	YD3	I am willing to recommend friends and relatives to seek healthcare at private hospitals	Ajen, I (1991); Cuong., N. T. K., (2013)
VIII	HV	Behavior of choosing treatment at Private Hospitals	
28	HV1	Seeking healthcare at private hospitals is entirely appropriate	
29	HV2	I will continue to seek healthcare at private hospitals in the near future	
30	HV3	I will recommend friends/relatives to seek healthcare at private hospitals	

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Based on the theory and research overview of the factors affecting the behavior of seeking healthcare at private hospitals, the factors included in the research model are variables: (i) Attitude towards private hospitals; (ii) Subjective norms; (iii) Perceived behavioral control; (iv) Perceived benefits; (v) Healthcare costs; (vi) Motivation for seeking healthcare at private hospitals; and the intermediary variable: Intention to seek healthcare at private hospitals, which influence the dependent variable: Behavior of seeking healthcare at private hospitals in Hanoi.

A survey was constructed with a 5-point Likert scale, with:

1. Strongly disagree
2. Disagree
3. Neutral
4. Agree
5. Strongly agree

A quantitative research method was conducted to gather opinions from people in Hanoi who have the intention or have previously sought healthcare at private hospitals. After constructing the survey, the research team conducted a random pilot survey with 10 individuals who have sought healthcare at private hospitals. The preliminary survey results show that the participants agree with the factors included in the model.

Due to time and resource constraints for the survey, the author used a convenience sampling method. The minimum sample size needed is calculated using the formula $n = 50 + 8m$ ($n=50+8m$ (m: number of independent variables) (Tabachnick and Fidell, 1996). For this study, which has 8 variables, the minimum number of responses needed is $50 + 8 \times 8 = 114$ $50+8 \times 8=114$ responses. The survey targeted residents in Hanoi who have previously sought healthcare at private hospitals. To ensure a higher level of stability in the observed effects, the survey aimed to collect as many responses as possible. The survey was distributed to the target respondents online via a link: <https://forms.gle/ao18pDXd6pGX95U>. A total of 220 responses were collected, of which 173 responses were from individuals who had previously sought healthcare at private hospitals and were included in the analysis of intentions and behaviors. The remaining 47 responses were from individuals who had never sought healthcare at private hospitals and were only surveyed about their reasons for not doing so.

3.2 Data Processing Method

A quantitative research method was used to process the data collected from the survey of Hanoi residents who had previously sought healthcare at private hospitals. The general form of the structural regression equation is:

$$YD = a*TD + b*CCQ+c*NT+ d*LI+e*CP+f*DC$$

$$HV=g*YD$$

The SMARTPLS software was used to test the hypotheses and evaluate the impact of the factors.

Step 1: Evaluating Measurement Model

Evaluating measurement model based on examining values of reliability, quality of observed variable, convergence, and discriminant

- Testing the quality of observed variables (Outer Loadings)

Outer Loadings of observed variables are indicators showing the degree of association between observed variables and latent variables (proxy variables). Basically, outer loadings in SMARTPLS are the square root of the absolute value of R² linear regression from the latent variables to the sub-observed variables.

Hair et al. (2016) suggest that the outer loadings should be greater than or equal to 0.708 observed variables that are quality. To make it easier to remember, the researchers rounded off the threshold to 0.7 instead of the number 0.708.

- Evaluating Reliability

Evaluating the reliability through SMARTPLS by two main indicators, Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability (CR). Composite Reliability (CR) is preferred by many researchers over Cronbach's Alpha because Cronbach's Alpha underestimates the reliability compared with CR. Chin (1998) claims that in exploratory research CR must be over 0.6. For confirmed studies, the 0.7 threshold is the appropriate level of CR (Henseler & Sarstedt, 2013). Other researchers agree that 0.7 is the appropriate threshold for the vast majority of cases such as Hair et al. (2010), and Bagozzi & Yi (1988).

Thus, the reliability through SMARTPLS is shown by Cronbach's Alpha ≥ 0.7 (DeVellis, 2012); Composite Reliability CR ≥ 0.7 (Bagozzi & Yi, 1988).

- Testing Convergence

Evaluating Convergence on SMARTPLS is based on Ave (Average Variance Extracted). Hock & Ringle (2010) claim that a scale reaches a convergence value if AVE reaches 0.5 or higher. This level of 0.5 (50%) means that the average latent variable will explain at least 50% of the variation of each sub-observed variable. Thus, convergence is evaluated by Average Variance Extracted AVE ≥ 0.5 (Hock & Ringle, 2010).

- Testing Discriminant Validity

Discriminant value is used to consider whether a research variable is really different from other research variables in the model. To evaluate the discriminant validity, Sarstedt & et al (2014) said that considering two criteria including cross-loadings and the measurement of Fornell and Larcker (1981).

Cross-loading coefficients are often the first approach to evaluating the discriminant validity of indicators (observed variables) (Hair, Hult, et al., 2017). The load factor of the observed variable (indicator) linked in the factor (latent variable) should be greater than any of its cross-load factors (its correlation) in the other factors.

Fornell and Larcker (1981) recommend that discriminant is ensured when the square root of AVE for each latent variable is higher than all correlations between latent variables. In addition, Henseler & et al (2015) used simulation studies to demonstrate that discriminant validity is better evaluated by the HTMT index that they developed.

With the HTMT index, Garson (2016) said that the discriminant validity between two latent variables is guaranteed when the HTMT index is less than 1. Henseler & et al (2015) propose that if this value is below 0.9, the discriminant validity will be guaranteed. Meanwhile, Clark & Watson (1995) and Kline (2015) used a stricter standard threshold of 0.85. SMARTPLS preferred a threshold of 0.85 in the evaluation.

- Testing Multicollinearity

In this study, the author uses a scale related to multicollinearity as a variance magnification factor (VIF). Very high levels of multicollinearity are indicated by VIF values ≥ 5 ; the model does not have multicollinearity when VIF indicators < 5 (Hair et al., 2016).

Step 2: Evaluating Structural Model

After evaluating the satisfactory measurement model, evaluate the structural model through the impact relationship, path coefficient, R squared, and f squared.

- Evaluating impactful relationships

To evaluate impact relationships, use the results of Bootstrap analysis. Based mainly on two columns (1) Original Sample (normalized impact factor) and (2) P Values (sig value compared to 0.05 significance level).

- Original Sample: Standardized impact factor of the original data. SMARTPLS have no unstandardized impact factor.
- Sample Mean: The average standardized impact factor of all samples from Bootstrap.
- Standard Deviation: Standard deviation of the standardized impact factor (according to the original sample).
- T Statistics: Test value t (test student the meaning of the impact).
- P Values: The significance level of the T Statistics. This significance level is considered with comparative thresholds such as 0.05, 0.1, or 0.01 (usually used as 0.05).

Evaluating the level of interpretation of the independent variable for the dependent variable by R2 coefficient (R square). To evaluate the R2 coefficient, we will use the results of the PLS Algorithm analysis. The R2 value evaluates the predictive accuracy of the model and shows the level of interpretation of the independent variable for the dependent variable. R square is between 0 and 1, the closer to 1 indicates the more independent variables that account for the dependent variable (Hair, Hult, et al, 2017).

Additionally, to evaluate the impact level of each factor, the group conducted an analysis to determine the distance value and the average value of each factor and identify which response threshold the average score falls into.

$$\text{Distance value} = (\text{Maximum} - \text{Minimum}) / n = (5-1)/5 = 0.8$$

Assessment thresholds based on average score values:

- + 1.00 - 1.80: Strongly disagree
- + 1.81 - 2.60: Disagree
- + 2.61 - 3.40: Neutral
- + 3.41 - 4.20: Agree
- + 4.21 - 5.00: Strongly agree

4. RESEARCH RESULTS

4.1. Survey Participant Statistics

The survey link received 220 responses, with details on gender, occupation, age, living area, and monthly income as follows:

Table 9: Descriptive Statistics of Survey Participants

Occupation			Age		
Income	N. of People	Percentage (%)	Age	N. of People	Percentage (%)
< 10 million VND	83	37,7%	Under 30 years old	62	28,2%
10-< 20 million VND	88	40%	From 30 to under 40 years old	38	17,3%
20-<50 million VND	40	18,2%	From 40 to under 50 years old	90	40,9%
>= 50 million VND	9	4,1%	From 50 to under 60 years old	25	11,4%
			Over 60 years old	5	2,3%
Occupation	N. of People	Percentage (%)	Gender	N. of People	Percentage (%)
Student	49	22,3%	Woman	101	45,9%
Worker	164	74,5%	Man	117	53,2%
Retired	7	3,2%	Prefer not to say	2	0,9%

Source: Survey Results

The occupation of survey participants was mainly workers with 164 people (74.5%), 49 people (22.3%) were students, and 7 people (3.2%) were retired.

The age of survey participants was mostly under 60 years old: 62 responses (28.2%) were from people under 30 years old; 38 responses (17.3%) were from people whose age was from 30 to under 40 years old; 90 responses (40.9%) were from people between 40 to 50 years old; 25 responses (11.4%) were from those aged 50 to under 60 years old; and 5 responses (2.3%) were from those over 60 years old.

The income of survey participants was mainly under 20 million VND per month, specifically, 83 responses (37.7%) had an income of less than 10 million VND; 88 responses (40%) had an income of 10-<20 million VND; incomes over 20 million VND accounted for a smaller proportion.

Additionally, among the 220 responses, 55% lived in the suburbs; 44.1% lived in the urban city. Among the 220 responses, 173 people (78.6%) had previously received medical treatment at private hospitals in Hanoi, while 47 people (21.4%) had not. The reasons for not seeking treatment at private hospitals are shown in the chart below:

Figure 2: Reasons for Not Seeking Treatment at Private Hospitals

Source: Survey Results

The primary reasons for not seeking treatment at private hospitals were “prices are high” with 21 responses (44.7%); “Inconvenient to travel” and “Inconvenient for health insurance payment” both received 15 responses (31.9%); “Health condition is suitable for treatment at public hospitals” had 9 responses (19.1%); “Simply do not like it” had 8 responses (17%); “Quality of treatment is not guaranteed” had 4 responses (8.5%). Other reasons, for example, “Rarely get sick, so no need for treatment” with 1 response (2.1%).

4.2. Survey Results

4.2.1. Evaluation of Observed Variable Quality in the Measurement Model

The quality of the observed variables was evaluated through the outer loadings coefficient. The quality of the observed variables affecting choice behavior for treatment at private hospitals is shown in Table 10.

Table 10: Outer Loadings Coefficients for Factors Affecting Choice Behavior for Treatment at Private Hospitals

	CCQ	CP	DC	HV	LI	NT	TD	YD
CCQ1	0,942							
CCQ2	0,944							
CCQ3	0,942							
CP1		0,926						
CP2		0,940						
CP3		0,947						
DC1			0,893					
DC2			0,933					
DC3			0,942					
DC4			0,947					
DC5			0,920					
HV1				0,947				
HV2				0,958				
HV3				0,953				
LI1					0,933			
LI2					0,921			
LI3					0,890			
LI4					0,924			
NT1						0,907		
NT2						0,919		
NT3						0,935		
NT4						0,942		
TD2							0,925	
TD3							0,924	
TD4							0,916	
TD5							0,912	
YD1								0,942
YD2								0,956
YD3								0,945
TD1							0,910	

Source: Research Group's Test Results

The results from Table 10 show that the outer loadings coefficients of all observed variables affecting the choice behavior for treatment at private hospitals are greater than 0.7, indicating that the observed variables are significant.

Reliability Testing of the Scale

The reliability of the scales for factors affecting the choice behavior for treatment at private hospitals was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability (CR) on SMARTPLS.

Table 11: Reliability Coefficients (Cronbach's Alpha) and Composite Reliability of Factors Affecting the Choice Behavior for Treatment at Private Hospitals

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
CCQ	0,937	0,937	0,960	0,888
CP	0,932	0,935	0,957	0,880
DC	0,959	0,959	0,968	0,860
HV	0,949	0,950	0,967	0,908
LI	0,937	0,937	0,955	0,841
NT	0,944	0,946	0,960	0,857
TD	0,953	0,953	0,964	0,842
YD	0,943	0,943	0,963	0,898

Source: Research Group's Test Results

According to Table 11, after analyzing the reliability of the factors using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient, the results are Subjective Norms (CCQ) at 0.937; Cost (CP) at 0.932; Motivation for Treatment (DC) at 0.959; Perceived Benefits (LI) at 0.937; Perceived Behavioral Control (NT) at 0.944; Attitude towards Treatment at Private Hospitals (TD) at 0.953; Intention of choosing treatment at Private Hospitals (YD) at 0.943; and Behavior of Choosing Treatment at Private Hospitals (HV) at 0.949. Thus, all scales satisfy the condition of being greater than 0.7 and no variable violates the rule for elimination, so no variables were excluded, and the reliability is acceptable.

The Composite Reliability (CR) of all observed variables is also greater than 0.7, indicating that the scales are reliable and can be used for further factor analysis.

Convergent Validity

According to the data analysis results in Table 11, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for factors: Subjective Norms (CCQ) at 0.888; Cost (CP) at 0.880; Motivation for Treatment (DC) at 0.860; Perceived Benefits (LI) at 0.841; Perceived Behavioral Control (NT) at 0.857; Attitude towards Treatment at Private Hospitals (TD) at 0.842; Intention of choosing Treatment at Private Hospitals (YD) at 0.898; Behavior of Choosing Treatment at Private Hospitals (HV) at 0.908. Therefore, all factors satisfy the condition of having AVE greater than 0.5, indicating the factors have good convergence and are suitable for the model.

Discriminant Validity

The results in Table 12 regarding the Fornell-Larcker criterion for the model studying the factors affecting: Subjective Norms (CCQ); Cost (CP); Motivation for Treatment (DC); Perceived Benefits (LI); Perceived Behavioral Control (NT); Attitude towards Treatment at Private Hospitals (TD); Intention of choosing Treatment at Private Hospitals (YD); Behavior of Choosing Treatment at Private Hospitals (HV) all ensure discriminant validity because all the square root values of AVE on the diagonal are higher than their off-diagonal values. Therefore, in terms of discriminant validity, considering the two criteria of cross-loadings and the Fornell-Larcker criterion, the conditions are satisfied.

Table 12: Discriminant Validity of Factors Affecting the Choice Behavior for Treatment at Private Hospitals

	CCQ	CP	DC	HV	LI	NT	TD	YD
CCQ	0,942							
CP	0,834	0,938						
DC	0,763	0,871	0,927					
HV	0,854	0,884	0,875	0,953				
LI	0,729	0,832	0,904	0,829	0,917			
NT	0,819	0,836	0,838	0,840	0,838	0,926		
TD	0,776	0,832	0,828	0,816	0,827	0,800	0,917	
YD	0,821	0,885	0,895	0,918	0,875	0,836	0,833	0,948

Source: Research Group's Test Results

Function value f^2

The f^2 value indicates the extent of influence of a construct (factor) when removed from the model. The values of f^2 corresponding to 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35 represent small, medium, and large effect sizes (Cohen, 1988) of an exogenous variable. If the effect size is less than 0.02, it is considered no influence.

Table 13: Summary Table of f^2 Values

	CCQ	CP	DC	HV	LI	NT	TD	YD
CCQ								0,072
CP								0,064
DC								0,083
HV								
LI								0,064
NT								0,000
TD								0,007
YD				5,331				

Source: Research Group's Test Results

In this model, according to Table 13, the factor "Intention to use private hospital services" (YD) (5.331) has an f^2 value > 0.35 , indicating that this factor has a large effect on "Choosing to use private hospital services" (HV).

The factors "Subjective norm" (CCQ) reached 0.072; "Cost" (CP) reached 0.064; "Perceived benefits" (LI) reached 0.064; and "Motivation to seek medical treatment" (DC) reached 0.083. These factors, with $0.02 < f^2 < 0.15$, have a small effect on YD.

The factors "Perceived behavioral control" (NT) (0.000) and "Attitude towards private hospital services" (TD) (0.007) have f^2 values < 0.02 , suggesting they have no significant influence on YD.

4.2.2. Evaluation of Influence Levels Using Structural Model

Assessment of Influence Relationships between factors

The relationships and their influence levels of factors affecting the behavior of choosing private hospital services in SMARTPLS are depicted in Figure 2

Figure 3: Influence Relationships between factors

Source: Results of SMARTPLS testing by the research team

The results of Bootstrap analysis evaluating the influential relationships are presented in Table 14. According to this analysis, variables such as Perceived Standard (CCQ), Cost (CP), Treatment Motivation (DC), Perceived Benefits (LI), and Intention of Choosing Treatment at Private Hospitals (YD) have an influence on “Behavior of Choosing Treatment at Private Hospitals” (HV).

These factors have P Values < 0.05, indicating statistically significant relationships in the same direction towards the behavior of choosing private hospital services (Hypotheses H2, H4, H5, H6 are accepted). The factors “Perceived Behavioral Control” and “Attitude towards Seeking Treatment at Private Hospitals” have P Values > 0.1, indicating that these factors do not have sufficient statistical significance to demonstrate a relationship with the behavior of choosing private hospital services (Hypotheses H1, H3 are not accepted).

Table 14: Path Coefficients of Structural Model

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
CCQ -> YD	0,194	0,190	0,082	2,360	0,019
CP -> YD	0,226	0,215	0,087	2,600	0,010
DC -> YD	0,282	0,292	0,099	2,834	0,005
LI -> YD	0,233	0,222	0,092	2,523	0,012
NT -> YD	0,009	0,007	0,078	0,118	0,906
TD -> YD	0,061	0,077	0,088	0,690	0,491
YD -> HV	0,918	0,916	0,018	51,272	0,000

Source: Testing results of the research team

The test results in Table 14 have shown that with 95% credibility, the factor “Motivation for Seeking Healthcare at Private Hospitals” (DC) has the strongest influence on “Intention of choosing treatment at Private Hospitals” (YD) with an impact coefficient of 0.282, following by the factors “Perceived benefits” (LI) have an impact coefficient of 0.233; “Healthcare Costs” (CP) has an impact coefficient of 0.226, and “Subjective norms” (CCQ) has an impact coefficient of 0.194. “Intention of choosing treatment at Private Hospitals” (YD) influences the behavior of choosing treatment at Private Hospitals with an impact coefficient of 0.918. The factors “Perceived behavioral control” and “Attitude towards private hospital care” do not have statistically significant effects on the “Intention of choosing treatment at Private Hospitals” (YD). Therefore, we have the regression equation as follows:

$$YD = 0.194*CCQ + 0.226*CP + 0.282*DC + 0.233*LI$$

$$HV = 0.918*YD$$

Evaluation of the overall coefficient determines R² (R-squared)

The results of the PLS Algorithm analysis for the R² value reflect the extent to which the independent variables explain the dependent variable. The R² index measures the overall coefficient of determination (R-square value), which is an indicator to measure the model's fit to the data (the model's explanatory power). According to Hair et al. (2010), the R-square value is suggested to be at the levels of 0.75, 0.50, or 0.25.

Table 15: Explanation coefficient of the independent variable for the dependent variable (R²)

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
HV	0,842	0,841
YD	0,873	0,868

Source: Testing results of the research team

With the variable “Behavior of choosing medical examination and treatment at private hospitals” (HV), the results from table 15 show that R² is 0.842 and adjusted R² is 0.841, so the variables included in the model explain 84.2% of the difference. Fluctuations of HV variable. For the variable “Intention to Seek Medical Treatment at Private Hospitals” (YD), results from

Table 15 show an R^2 value of 0.873 and an adjusted R^2 value of 0.868, indicating that the independent variables in the model explain 87.3% of the variance in the YD variable.

Evaluation of Reliability Index (SRMR):

The Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) index indicates the model’s fit. According to Hu & Bentler (1999), a model is considered well-fitted if the SRMR value is less than 0.08.

Table 16: Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) Reliability Index:

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0,040	0,046

Source: Testing results of the research team

The SRMR results in Table 16 show that the model's SRMR value is less than 0.08. Therefore, the model is suitable for data analysis.

5. DISCUSSION

Statistical results in Table 6 indicate that, with 95% credibility, the factor “Motivation for Seeking Medical Treatment at Private Hospitals” (DC), with an impact of 0.282, has the strongest effect on “Intention of choosing Medical Treatment at Private Hospitals” (YD). This means that when the motivation for seeking medical treatment increases by 1 unit, the intention to seek treatment at private hospitals increases by 0.282 units.

Figure 4: Average Values of Observed Variables for the “Motivation for Seeking Medical Treatment at Private Hospitals” (DC) Factor

Source: Testing results of the research team

Among the factors motivating people to choose private hospitals, DC2 (related to shorter waiting times), DC3 (related to convenience and flexibility in the treatment process), and DC4 (related to transparency in treatment costs) received the highest agreement from survey

participants. This reflects a significant issue in the healthcare system, where people increasingly value factors beyond the quality of medical services.

- **Shorter waiting times (Average score: 3.942)** are considered the most important factor for people when choosing private hospitals. This can be explained by the overload in the public healthcare system, where patients often have to wait a long time for consultations and treatment.
- **Convenience and flexibility (Average score: 3.925):** Private hospitals often provide services during weekends and evenings, home treatment, appointment scheduling with doctors, and ease in choosing specialists suitable for the patient's condition and personal needs.
- **Transparency in treatment costs (Average score: 3.89):** Private hospitals typically have clear pricing and provide detailed information on costs before treatment, helping patients manage finances better and avoid unexpected expenses.

Motivation due to high-quality medical services has the lowest average score, reaching 3.763. This may indicate that in people's eyes, the quality of medical services at private and public hospitals does not differ significantly. The quality of services at private hospitals can be assured through modern equipment, highly skilled medical staff, and attentive patient care. However, this is not enough to be the most important factor in people's choice of hospitals.

The “Perceived Benefits” (LI) factor has an impact of 0.233; meaning that when perceived benefits increase by 1 unit, the intention to seek treatment at private hospitals increases by 0.233 units. Factors such as shorter waiting times, better service, a comfortable environment, and convenient location are key drivers for people choosing private hospitals in Hanoi. These factors not only meet patient needs and expectations but also reflect the development and competitiveness of the private healthcare system.

Figure 5: Average Values of Observed Variables for the “Perceived Benefits” (LI) Factor

Source: Testing results of the research team

- Seeking treatment at private hospitals helps reduce waiting times (average score 3.942). This is the most concerning benefit for people and aligns with the time-saving motivation analyzed above.
- The environment at private hospitals makes me feel comfortable (average score 3.896). Private hospitals often invest in facilities, creating a modern, comfortable treatment environment. A comfortable space not only reduces patient stress and anxiety but also creates better conditions for recovery. This is especially important for patients needing long-term treatment or a quiet place to rest and recover.
- Seeking treatment at private hospitals provides better service (average score 3.861). Private hospitals often have professional and dedicated customer care policies. This is reflected in warm reception, detailed guidance from medical staff, and comprehensive healthcare services from initial intake to post-treatment follow-up.
- The location of private hospitals is convenient for my travel (average score 3.728). The convenient location of private hospitals is a major advantage. Many private hospitals are located in city centers, near main roads or densely populated areas, making it easier for patients to visit and for family members to provide support.

The “Cost of Medical Treatment” factor has an impact of 0.226, meaning that when the cost of medical treatment increases by 1 unit, the intention to seek treatment at private hospitals increases by 0.226 units.

Figure 6: Average Values of Observed Variables for the “Healthcare Costs” (CP) Factor

Source: Testing results of the research team

The cost of medical treatment at private hospitals in Hanoi is considered suitable for the financial capability, benefits, and experience of patients. Private hospitals not only provide high-quality medical services but also create positive treatment experiences, from comfortable environments and short waiting times to professional customer service. Transparency in costs and patients’ ability to pay, along with investment in technology and medical equipment, contribute to making private hospitals a preferred choice for many people.

The “Subjective Norms” (CCQ) factor has an impact of 0.194, meaning that when subjective norms increase by 1 unit, the intention to seek treatment at private hospitals increases by 0.194 units.

Figure 7: Average values of observed variables for the factor “Subjective Norms” (CCQ)

Source: Testing results of the research team

Results show that the intention to seek treatment at private hospitals among survey participants is most strongly influenced by friends and surrounding people (average score 3.613). When friends or relatives have had positive experiences at private hospitals and share this, it can strongly motivate others to choose private hospitals. Next, the influence comes from the belief that friends and relatives also intend to or are using this service (average score 3.59). When many people around, especially friends and relatives, use private hospital services, an individual tends to follow to avoid feeling isolated or different. The influence from recommendations by doctors, medical staff, or influencers in the medical field scores an average of 3.543. When a doctor or medical expert advises patients to choose private hospitals, patients feel more assured about the service quality and treatment outcomes. The above factors of CCQ suggest that private hospitals should expand communication channels, value online reviews, feedback, and recommendations, as well as the importance of word-of-mouth information.

The “Intention to Seek Medical Treatment at Private Hospitals” (YD) factor affects the actual behavior of choosing private hospitals with an impact of 0.918, meaning that when the intention to seek treatment at private hospitals increases by 1 unit, the actual behavior increases by 0.918 units. This is a very high impact, indicating that a strong intention leads to corresponding actual behavior. The higher the intention, the more likely people are to engage in behaviors such as seeking treatment at private hospitals, continuing to use the services in the future, and recommending them to others.

Figure 8: Average Values of Observed Variables for the “Intention of Choosing Medical Treatment at Private Hospitals” Factor

Source: Testing results of the research team

The intention to seek treatment at private hospitals is divided into three levels: “Intend to seek treatment at private hospitals in the near future”; “Will pay more attention to the services at private hospitals”; and highest, “Ready to recommend friends and relatives to seek treatment at private hospitals.” The results show that these three levels received average scores of 3.769, 3.78, and 3.769 respectively.

The intention of choosing treatment at private hospitals not only strongly influences actual behavior but also reflects people's satisfaction and trust in private healthcare services. High intention leads to corresponding behavior, from personally using the service to recommending it to others, creating a positive cycle that enhances reputation and attracts more patients to private hospitals.

6. CONCLUSION

Choosing to seek treatment at private hospitals is on the rise as people increasingly focus on health care. Based on the theory of planned behavior and a review of both international and domestic literature, this study investigates the factors influencing the intention to seek treatment at private hospitals (YD), including six factors: Subjective Norms (CCQ); Cost (CP); Motivation for Seeking Medical Treatment (DC); “Perceived Behavioral Control”; “Attitude towards Treatment at Private Hospitals”; and Perceived Benefits (LI). The results show that Subjective Norms (CCQ); Cost (CP); Motivation for Seeking Medical Treatment (DC); and Perceived Benefits (LI) influence the intention of choosing treatment at private hospitals (YD). The factors “Perceived Behavioral Control” and “Attitude towards Treatment at Private Hospitals” do not have significant statistical implications for concluding their impact on the “Intention to Seek Treatment at Private Hospitals” (YD). The “Intention of choosing Treatment at Private Hospitals” (YD) strongly influences the actual behavior of choosing treatment at private hospitals with an impact of 0.918. As mentioned in the research problem, the ultimate

goal of this study is to examine the impact of factors on the behavioral intention to seek treatment at private hospitals in Hanoi. Factors related to personal characteristics such as gender, occupation, age, place of residence (urban, suburban) affecting behavioral intention have not been studied. Therefore, future research directions could include testing mean differences to see if there is a relationship between personal characteristics and behavioral intention. Additionally, future research could expand the study area beyond Hanoi.

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